

NATO'S projects and initiatives within its security policy: Ukrainian experience

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Received: September 08, 2020 | Revised: September 25, 2020 | Accepted: September 30, 2020

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4560667

Abstract

The fundamental tasks that the founders of the North Atlantic Treaty laid in the foundation of its functions are collective defence and the preservation of peace and security. It demands joint, well-planned and organized actions of all member countries aimed at repelling external military aggression or armed attack with an appropriate package of forces and means (diplomatic, political and military).

The well-organized rebuff of an armed attack on a NATO member state or the implementation of measures to maintain peace and security in the Euro-Atlantic area and beyond requires clear and coordinated action by both government officials and armed forces of member-countries and partners.

The Alliance's ability to carry out common tasks lies in the light of effective defence planning, interaction and coordination at all levels of governance in political and military spheres, as well as standardization.

The Alliance actively relies on partnership and cooperation in every area of its activities.

The partnership acquires different forms and content. Some countries participate in the "Partnership for Peace Program" (PfP), which is based on an agreed Framework Document and Individual or Special Partnership Programs. Cooperation with the countries of the Mediterranean Dialogue, the Istanbul Cooperation Initiatives and the other Partners across the globe (Contact Countries Initiatives) are based on agreed work programs and plans. All practical bilateral and multilateral cooperation (partnership) programs with NATO differ based on the national interests, ambitions and priorities of the Partner-countries themselves. The only thing they have in common is the issue of standardization, namely the achievement of an appropriate level of compatibility, interchangeability or commonality, depending on the military-political ambitions in the field of cooperation of a particular Partner nation with NATO.

The process of gaining full membership of Ukraine in NATO, among other things, involves the implementation of Alliance standards in all areas of the Defense Department, the Armed Forces of Ukraine and the Ukrainian State as a whole. When we talk about the implementation of NATO standards, we mean the transformation of Ukraine's security and defense sector to the best world principles, procedures and practices. It is not only about reforming the Armed Forces, the defense industry, the intelligence community and special services of Ukraine, but also about effective civil democratic control and parliamentary oversight over the defense forces, ensuring transparency in decision making processes at all levels, improving the effectiveness of existing anti-corruption bodies, introducing effective operational planning process focused on needed operational capabilities, etc.

Key words: standards, integration, interoperability, interchangeability, NATO.

Introduction

NATO standards and their implementation security policy in today's world, aimed at processes are an essential part of the Alliance's maintaining a zone of stability and peace in the

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Euro-Atlantic area, as well as extending it beyond NATO's geographical area of responsibility. The issue of implementing NATO standards in day-to-day business applies to both Allies and Partners, as none of the Member States has fully implemented them. The average level of implementation of Alliance standards in the Armed Forces of the leading Member States fluctuates within 80% from the more than 1,500 existing now (Kovalenko H., 2019).

Ukraine's standardization process as well as NATO's standardization process consists of three levels of interaction and is based on the implementation of the "from the simplest to the most complex" principle. The object of NATO military standardization, that determines the degree of interaction is combat operational systems, databases and procedures / interfaces. Level One (the simplest) is the level of compatibility of military standardization objects, which involves the use of different combat systems, potentially different digital databases, but common procedures and interfaces. Level Two (the golden mean) is the level of interchangeability, which provides the possibility of using different combat systems, but common databases and joint procedures and interfaces. The Third level (the most complex) is the level of standardization, namely unification (commonality), in which the Armed Forces of member countries and partners use both common combat systems and databases, procedures and interfaces.

In March 2016, NATO has introduced a new Standardization Policy, which is primarily to

develop and implement procedures, practical solutions and military terminology in the light of achieving the required level of interoperability. The leadership of the Alliance emphasizes the importance of getting the most out of the compatibility and capability of the troops (forces). Therefore, it is standardization that should contribute to the achievement of an appropriate level of interoperability, its sustainment and further build-up between both Alliance and Partner nations forces, strengthening NATO's defense capabilities and enhancing combat readiness and effectiveness of joint actions (operations / missions).

Taken as a whole, NATO's standardization work in cooperation and partnership, together with other Allied political – military Initiatives, aims to create a safer security environment in the Euro-Atlantic area and, to some extent, beyond Alliance tradition boundaries.

In general, each NATO member and Partner nation has appropriate national systems in place to receive, record, maintain and disseminate Alliance standards, as well to plan and introduce measures to implement them. In particular, in the Armed Forces of Ukraine, NATO standards are implemented according to the methodology defined by the Standardization Body. To give this process a clear administrative and organizational character in 2016, the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine formed a single governing body responsible for the organization and coordination of standardization and codification in the military sphere – the Directorate for Standardization, Codification and Cataloging.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Taking into account the tasks facing the Ministry of Defense and the Armed Forces of Ukraine in this area, this topic was reflected in a number of scientific and research works of the Ukrainian researchers and scientists, in particular: O. Poshedin, A. Hetmanchuk, M. Fedorkin, M. Khilko, I. Saenko, L. Holopatiuk, M. Badyuk, O. Makogon, A. Slyusarenko, V. Lypynskyi. Particular attention is drawn to the publications of I. Saenko "Military reform of Ukraine: achievements and priorities of the

Ukrainian Armed Forces towards the implementation of NATO standards" (2017), the author's team led by L. Holopatiuk "Implementation of NATO standards in the daily activities of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in the context of increasing the level of interoperability with the Allied Armed forces"(2016) [6], M. Badyuk "Assessing the capabilities of the health care system according to NATO standards", M. Khilko "Compatibility and implementation of NATO standards in the interaction of Ukraine

with the North Atlantic Alliance” (2020) and V. Lypynsky “Application of NATO standards in creating a system of information protection in the field of national security”. The main leitmotif of these works is the urgent need to implement NATO standards in the field of achieving the Second Level of Standardization, namely interoperability with NATO forces, which will strengthen the defense capabilities of the Ukrainian state by implementing the best practices of NATO member countries. This approach is due to the vital need to be better acquainted with operational decision-making procedures, operational troop planning process, preparation of combat documents, topographic legends and staff’s culture of their mapping, proficiency in official NATO languages and so on.

Setting objectives. In the development of Ukraine’s Armed Forces at the present stage, the process of transition to NATO standards should contribute to interoperability with Allied forces at the operational, tactical and strategic levels through (1) the development and implementation of doctrinal documents, concepts, strategies and common procedures in the daily activities of military authorities and troops; (2) accession to NATO’s Standardization Agreements (STANAGs), which account for 65% of the total number of existing standards; (3) amending the provisions of national regulations or developing new one based on the requirements of NATO standards.

NATO’s multilateral Pol-Mil Initiatives play a special role in all of the above mentioned areas of implementation of NATO’s standards in military field, including the Force Planning and Review Process (PARP), the Operational Capabilities Concept (OCC), the Partnership Interoperability Initiative or Interchangeability Initiative (PII), the Interoperability Platform (IP) and the Enhanced Opportunities Partners (EOP) programs, as well as the bilateral “NATO +

Partner” formats such as the Comprehensive Assistance Package for Ukraine (CAP-U), NATO / PfP Trust Funds and number of practical results oriented Pilot projects such as Regional Air Security Program (RASP), Air Situation Data Exchange, Defense Enhanced Education Programme (DEEP), Language Training Initiative, etc.

Each of these mechanisms of cooperation with the NATO, in addition to addressing issues related to improvement of operational, administrative and technical interoperability through the implementation of certain Partnership Goals, training and certification of the military units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine to participate in joint military exercises and operations under the auspices of NATO, contributes to overall increasing the level of defense capabilities of Ukraine and her resilience against Russia’s hostile behavior and “hybrid” aggression.

Methodology. The content of the each practical projects, the identification and selection of Partnership Goals, the list of designated military units and means to participate in the PARP and the Evaluation and Feedback Program of the Operational Capability Concept are developed by NATO experts along with the Ukrainian experts and, if necessary, could be specified at least every two years on the basis of relevant Department of Defense Political-Military Guidance.

Each of the initiatives proposed to Ukraine by NATO side is just only so-called “window of opportunity” and in all parts will depend on Ukraine how effectively she can take advantage of them. The answer to this question lies in the level of readiness of the Ukrainian Defense and Military Authorities to carry out defense reforms within Defense Department and the Armed Forces of Ukraine and their active application.

Results and discussion

NATO Practical Projects and Initiatives. The NATO provides critical practical support and assistance to Ukraine through more than 40 special events (actions) of the Comprehensive

Assistance Package of Ukraine, approved by Heads of State and Government during the 2016 NATO Warsaw Summit. The package includes a number of NATO / PfP Trust Funds, Integrity and

Capacity building programs, consultative and advisory assistance.

Up to date, the CAP-U has “helped to align NATO’s advisory assistance with the identified goals and objectives of defense and security reforms in Ukraine in order to strengthen the capabilities of the security and defense sector, as well as increase the level of resilience to the Russia’s provocative military behavior and aggression” (Vinnykov A., 2019).

In order to practically support the reform efforts of the Government of Ukraine, the Alliance’s main CAP efforts focus on 13 areas of cooperation, namely: development of defense capabilities and state institutions, troops command and control system, communications and automation, logistics and standardization, defense technology, cyber defense, energy security, medical treatment and rehabilitation, mine security, destruction of explosive devices, including countering improvised explosive devices, security science, strategic communications, countering hybrid threats, emergency planning and security reform of Ukraine.

Currently, the implementation of the CAP-U is carried out in five main areas, namely: the development of Special Operations Forces, the restoration of naval capabilities, the creation of an integrated logistics and standardization system and the development of C2, communications, information and cyber security.

The implementation of CAP-U measures is significantly enhanced by the scale of bilateral and multilateral cooperation projects with individual NATO member – countries and the Alliance as a whole, in particular through the implementation of the objectives of the NATO / PfP Trust Funds, international security assistance, and military training – JMTG-U, Orbital, Unifier, LMTM-U, providing consultative and advisory assistance at the strategic, operational and tactical levels within the functioning of the Defense Reforms Advisory Board (DRAB), the Multinational Joint Coordination Committee (JMCC), the Multinational Coordination Cell (MCC), participation in joint military exercises on the

territory of Ukraine.

In 2014, in response to Russia’s military aggression against Ukraine and the illegal annexation of Crimea, NATO launched 8 specialized NATO Trust Funds under the PfP program. NATO / PfP Trust Funds have acted as a kind of treasury, depository of financial and other material and human resources of NATO member – countries and Partners. The NATO / PfP Trust Fund is headed by a member of the Alliance by a decision of the North Atlantic Council. Decisions on the formation of the general and annual budgets of the NATO / PfP Trust Funds, the use of the allocated resource, and their closure are taken collectively at NATO Headquarters, taking into account the national interests and persuasion of the recipient and donor countries (NATO Bullitien).

In order to form an effective resource potential in the field of human capacity development, material and technical equipment with the latest types of weapons and special equipment, proposals have been developed and put into the Operational capabilities Catalogue of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, in which clearly defines the legal framework for the service components of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, types of the troops and their operational capabilities, basic and principle requirements to them, as well as ways how to achieve them and deadline of their achievement. This document serves as a roadmap for use of the potential of NATO’s practical projects in the light of strengthening Ukraine’s Armed Forces operational capabilities.

NATO’s Science for Peace and Security program (SPS) typically offers grants to scientists from the Defense Department and other Security sector forces of Ukraine to cooperate in priority areas, including the achievement of Partnership Goals. Grants are also offered to the scientific community of NATO’s Partner Nations to implement computer network infrastructure and optimize electronic communications etc. The Alliance’s initiatives to increase the interoperability, interchangeability and commonality of weapons systems in NATO countries are implemented through the “Smart Defense” program. Its implementation is aimed

primarily at ensuring the principle of “collective defense and security, improving the defense planning system in NATO and introducing technological innovations in both decision-making processes and weapon systems.

The strategic dimension of “Smart Defense” is, first of all and foremost, finding ways to obtain a more effective defense and security systems in relatively short period of time and limited financial resources and increase investment in defense and security to better prepare for challenges and threats in the future. Prioritization, specialization and multinational cooperation will be the main pillars of the implementation of this initiative.

Principle implementation mechanisms of the NATO practical projects. The main practical mechanism for determining operational requirements for participation in multinational projects for NATO members remains the Alliance’s defense planning system, and for Partner countries – the Planning and Review Process (PARP).

Working along with the Alliance’s multinational “Smart Defense” projects requires Ukraine to further deepen military-technical cooperation with NATO both in the framework of the Conference of National Armaments Directors (Representatives) and the NATO-Ukraine Joint Working Group on Defense-Technical Cooperation. Gaining better and more sufficient results from participation of Ukraine in such practical projects are subject to improvement of number directorates of the Defense Department and the General Staff of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, especially within the framework of the PARP and OCC programs.

In the context of strengthening the operational capabilities of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and implementing NATO standards, very important role is played by the “Enhanced Opportunities Partners” program, in particular it is aimed to promote: a) intensification of Political-Military and purely Military dialogues at both strategic and operational-tactical levels. NATO will welcome Ukraine’s contribution to the periodic assessment of the security situation in the Black Sea region, on the one hand. On the

other hand, maintaining an active dialogue with NATO on the annexed Crimea, participation in the EOP program should allow Ukraine to exchange information, including sensitive one, at the early stages of emerging crises; b) intensification of combat training activities, including with the participation of units of the NATO members in military exercises on the territory of Ukraine and close vicinity to her. Particular interest Ukraine has in involvement of Ukrainian representatives to planning these exercises at the early stages; c) expanding of the presence of servicemen of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in the Headquarters and structures of the Alliance. NATO emphasizes that assignment to certain Headquarters in which Ukraine is interested are currently available only to 7-Non-NATO Nation (Austria, Australia, Ireland, New Zealand, Sweden, Switzerland, Finland) who have enhanced security agreements with the Alliance; d) exchange of intelligence information. NATO emphasizes the need to improve the existing legal framework, especially in the context of its protection critical information, as well as to make adjustments to NATO’s security procedures and policies. It was emphasized that there is a possibility to expand the exchange of information in the framework of NATO’s operation in the Mediterranean “Sea Guardian”. This can be done if the Alliance makes a political decision and recognizes Ukraine as a full operational partner. In addition, it is noted that in order to implement the project on the air situation data exchange under the ASDE Program, there is a need to address the technical component of this issue. NATO’s Strategic Operations Command is interested in exchanging information with Ukraine on traditional and hybrid threats. NATO Command is also interested to provide an in-depth exchange of information through the Joint Analysis Lesson Learned Center (JALLC) in Monsanto, Portugal. These areas form a potential field for improving the forms, methods and techniques of strengthening the operational capabilities of the Defense Department of Ukraine.

Conclusions

Ukraine is committed to implement NATO standards. The transition of the Armed Forces of Ukraine to the practice of applying NATO standards in everyday life will contribute to the general increase of their operational capabilities, increase the overall level of the country's defense capabilities, which is especially important in the situation of Russia's military aggression against Ukraine.

NATO's practical projects such as the PARP, OCC, the Interoperability Partnership Initiative, the Interoperability Platform, the Enhanced Opportunities Partners, the CAP-U, the NATO / PfP Trust Funds and the different Pilot projects are aimed at promoting defense reform in Ukraine, assisting and supporting of the Ukrainian Armed Forces. Implementation of the NATO standards in the day-to-day practice of military personnel will be reasonably

contributing to a safer security environment in the Euro-Atlantic area.

Prospects for further research. Describing the status of the problem studied in this article, presence of a sufficient number of other articles on this subject in military mass-media, other open sources publications, scientific works of the Ukrainian and Foreign SME it is established that the question of the peculiarities of NATO's security policy implementation in the context of practical projects in Ukraine, including implementation of NATO standards within the Defense Department of Ukraine and the Armed Forces of Ukraine, as well as their impact on the processes of building the operational capabilities of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, comprehensive coverage have not yet been received and need to continue research.

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